
98. Boyajian’s Star(s)

NASA’S KEPLER mission targeted the discovery of exoplanets through the transit method, and was operated between 2009–2018. It observed some 530 000 stars, and detected more than 2500 planets.

Amongst its many discoveries, remarkable for their sheer number but especially for the richness of the physical phenomena uncovered, are numerous ‘hot Jupiters’ and other planets orbiting very close to their host stars, often with periods of only some 3–4 days, or less!

Having been ‘delivered’ there, by some mix of tidal migration, scattering, and resonance effects, they will eventually spiral in towards their host stars as the angular momentum of their orbital motion is transferred to the host star rotation through tidal coupling.

The end result is some combination of tidal disruption, disintegration, and planet engulfment. The disintegration of such highly irradiated planets releases large amounts of gas and dust into an exospheric tail.

THE FIRST SUCH (presumed) disintegrating planet was around the 16 mag star Kepler–1520, which exhibits transit-like features every 15.7 h, varying in depth between 0.2–1.2%. It was promptly explained as a disintegrating rocky planet with a trailing cloud of dust of varying optical depth, created and constantly replenished by thermal surface erosion (Rappaport et al., 2012).

Amongst a few other such candidates was the curious KIC–8462852, discovered through the contribution of the amateur ‘Planet Hunters’ collaboration on the basis of its unusual light-curve (Boyajian et al., 2016), and subsequently often known as Boyajian’s star. The discovery paper reported pronounced dimming by up to 20%, lasting between 5–80 d, and with an irregular cadence and unusual profile. It has been subsequently monitored intensively at both radio and optical wavelengths.

Considerable speculation continues to accompany the unusual lightcurve. Interpretations range from occulting clouds of exocomets, a disrupted exomoon, and effects due an orbiting binary star. It has even been attributed to a ‘swarm of megastructures’, and hence as an outstanding SETI target (Wright et al., 2016).

WHILE THE ATTRIBUTION of the curious and complex lightcurve to some sort of alien-civilisation structure is not considered mainstream, the existence of such new and difficult-to-explain variability phenomena has certainly inspired the continued search for possible signatures of alien life.

Meanwhile, I will focus here on the search for, and Gaia’s contribution to, additional examples of the sorts of lightcurves exhibited by Boyajian’s star, characterised by infrequent episodes of small brightness dips and a long-term decline in brightness between the dips.

EVEN 4–5 YEARS after its discovery, no fully satisfactory mechanism has been established for its behaviour. Explanations are made more challenging because there was only this one known example.

To search for other stars showing similar ‘dipping’ behaviour, Schmidt (2016) used the extensive photometric data from the Northern Sky Variability Survey (NSVS) and the All Sky Automated Survey for Supernovae (ASAS-SN).

He reported 21 stars identified as possible dippers, with 15 showing similarity to Boyajian’s star (he classified these as ‘slow dippers’, with narrow dips of less than a few days, and fewer than three ‘dips’ per year), and the other 6 likely to be more extreme examples of the same phenomenon (‘rapid dippers’ with more than eight ‘dips’ per year). With this search covering some 15 times more stars than Kepler, his 15 ‘slow dippers’ are consistent with finding just the one amongst the Kepler sample.

A further extension to the search, over a larger region of the sky, yielded an additional 15 new ‘slow dipper’ candidates (Schmidt, 2022).

USING DISTANCES from Gaia Early Data Release 3 to establish their luminosities (and slightly modifying the preliminary conclusions in his first paper), Schmidt (2022) showed that the dipper candidates occupy a restricted region of the Hertzsprung–Russell diagram, a region which embraces both main sequence stars of around 1 solar mass, and stars in the red giant region near the evolutionary track for stars of around 2 solar mass. He considered those near the main sequence as likely to be analogues of Boyajian's star.

The various groupings are shown in the above figure, along with a statistical sample of stars representative of the selected dippers selected from Gaia DR2. His analysis suggests that the dipper stars are clustered significantly more in the Hertzsprung–Russell diagram than a random sample, therefore concluding that his searches have isolated a physically meaningful group of stars.

THINGS GET a little more interesting, and undoubtedly a little more contentious, when it comes to examining the distribution of these stars on the sky. Here, Schmidt (2022) drew attention to an apparent clump of 12 dippers between $254 - 303^{\circ}$ in right ascension (plus Boyajian's star, incidentally at a Gaia DR3 distance of 444 ± 2 pc, or 2.2545 ± 0.0099 mas), while the density of stars elsewhere is much lower. He rules out the appearance of the clump as originating from the higher star density near the Galactic plane.

Using the Gaia EDR3 parallaxes, the next step was to calculate the three-dimensional coordinates of the dipper candidates, using a frame in which the origin is at the Sun, the x axis is in the direction of the centre of the clump, y is towards the west, and z towards the north.

Four of the 12 clump stars are more than 1000 pc from the Sun, and clearly separated from the others. The remaining 8 stars in the clump, as well as Boyajian's star, form a structure that is about 50% longer in the x direction than in the y or z directions. The parallax uncertainties are all smaller than 0.8%, much too small to explain the apparent elongation of the clump.

Schmidt continues: 'Since no fully satisfactory explanation for the behaviour of Boyajian's star... has been found, it is premature to try to explain the existence of the clump. However, the possibility that extraterrestrial civilisations might have developed interstellar travel and expanded beyond their original planetary systems has been widely discussed in connection with the search for extraterrestrial intelligence. If this is actually possible, it could lead to a clump of stars with inhabited planets over an extended region of space... With these considerations in mind, I suggest that the dippers in the clump and other stars in the same region would be appropriate targets for SETI searches.'

THE SEARCH FOR unusual photometric lightcurves is undoubtedly still in its infancy. And the application above illustrates the power of Gaia in establishing the location of identified targets in the Hertzsprung–Russell diagram, and indeed their location in space.

Such surveys will be advanced dramatically by the Vera C. Rubin Observatory (previously LSST), where full survey operations are to begin in October 2024. But stimulated by the discovery of complex variables like Boyajian's star, renewed emphasis is also being placed on more robust algorithmic searches.

For example, Chakraborty et al. (2022) report a detection algorithm which makes minimal assumptions about the shape of a periodic signal. Applied to 240 000 TESS sources from the first-year southern sky survey, they found 377 previously unreported periodic signals, amongst which 26 are ultra-short periods, 313 are likely eclipsing binaries, 28 appear planet-like, and 10 are miscellaneous signals. Interestingly, none display the unusual behaviour displayed by Boyajian's star.

In their 'Vanishing and Appearing Sources during a Century of Observations' project, Villarroel et al. (2020) are using existing survey data to search for exceptional astrophysical transients, perhaps extending to evidence of technologically advanced civilisations.

THERE IS at least one other case where multiple unexplained sources appear to be clustered on the sky. Villarroel et al. (2021) identified 9 (apparent) transient sources in a region about ten minutes of arc across on a plate taken in April 1950 as part of the Palomar Observatory Sky Survey. All are absent on both previous and later photographic images, and absent in modern surveys with CCD detectors which go several magnitudes deeper. Were the plates subjected to an unknown type of contamination? Did they result from solar reflections from objects near geosynchronous orbits? Or what?

IN MY NEXT essay, I will look at one other specific search for alien civilisations that is ongoing, and also aided by the Gaia results: the search for Dyson spheres.